

Apparent molar volumes and viscosities of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF+water) mixed solvent systems at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

Vineeta, Radha Rani Gupta and Mukhtar Singh*

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : mukhtarsingh2003@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 14 December 2009, revised 8 March 2010, accepted 8 March 2010

Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and viscosities (η) of solutions of mono- and disaccharides viz. glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose have been determined in water and in dimethyl formamide (DMF+water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition (10, 20 and 30%, w/w) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K as a function of molality (m) of saccharides.

The $V_\phi - m$ and $\eta - m$ data have been analysed in the light of equations, $V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m$ and $\frac{(\eta_{rel} - 1)}{\sqrt{m}} = A + B\sqrt{m}$ respectively. The activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems have been determined at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The results in regard to solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in water and in (DMF+water) mixed solvent systems have been discussed in terms of the values of V_ϕ^0 , S_v and those of A and B . The results of the study reveal that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure makers in water and also (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems.

Keywords : Apparent molar volumes, viscosities, saccharides, (DMF + water) mixed solvents.

Introduction

Thermodynamic¹⁻⁴ and spectroscopic^{5,6} studies have shown that the hydration of saccharides depends upon the number of hydroxy groups⁷, the hydrogen bonding sites and the relative position of the hydroxy groups within the carbohydrate molecule⁸. The denaturation of certain proteins in the presence of denaturants like urea and guanidine hydrochloride is reduced in the presence of sugars and polyhydroxy alcohols^{9,10}. In this regard, Banipal and coworkers¹¹⁻¹⁵ have carried out studies relating to the measurement of partial molar volumes of some saccharides in water and in aqueous solutions of urea, guanidine hydrochloride, sodium chloride, cupric chloride and in zinc chloride. Syal *et al.*¹⁶ have reported viscosities of solutions of mannose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and in (water + acetonitrile) and (water + dimethyl sulphoxide) mixed solvents at different temperatures. The results of the study have been discussed on the basis of the values of the coefficient A and B of Jones-Dole equation¹⁷.

From the above stated survey of the literature it ap-

pears that studies relating to the determination of apparent molar volumes and viscosities of solutions of mono- and disaccharide in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems vis-a-vis solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions are still lacking. With this aim in view, the title study has been undertaken in the light of the following aspects :

(i) Determination of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) from density data as a function of molality (m) of solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and also in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition (10, 20 and 30%, w/w) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K;

(ii) Determination of limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in purely aqueous medium as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures;

(iii) Determination of partial molar volumes of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose from water to (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures;

*Address for correspondence . H.I.G. 142, Phase A, Shastri Puram, Sikandra, Agra-282 007, Uttar Pradesh, India.

(iv) Determination of viscosities of solutions of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures and subsequent analysis of viscosity-molality data in the light of Jones-Dole equation; and

(v) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ per mole of solvent and solute respectively, at different temperatures and subsequent calculation of entropy ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and enthalpy ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of activation of viscous flow at different temperatures.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous medium as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems (m_s) have been determined as a function of molality (m) from the density data at different temperatures using the following equation^{14,15},

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{m\rho\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where m is the molality of the solutions, M is the molecular weight of the mono- and disaccharides; ρ_0 and ρ are

the densities of solvent and solution respectively. The representative data in respect of one of the typical saccharides (glucose) are presented in Table 1. The plots of V_ϕ versus m according to eq. (2)^{14,15} are found to be linear with intercept equal to V_ϕ^0 in purely aqueous medium as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures (Fig. 1),

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume at infinite dilution (which is equal to partial molar volume of the solute, V_2^0) and S_v is the experimental slope¹⁸ (sometimes^{19,20} considered to be the volumetric pairwise interaction coefficient). V_ϕ^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions²¹ while S_v is a measure of solute-solute interactions²². The parameters, V_ϕ^0 and S_v have been evaluated by computerized least squares fitting of V_ϕ , versus m data to the above equation and the values are listed in Table 2 along with the standard errors (given in parentheses).

The larger and positive values of V_ϕ^0 for mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous medium as well as in the presence of (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems indi-

Table 1. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of mono- and disaccharides as a function of molality (m) in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Saccharides	Molality (m) (mol kg ⁻¹)	Temp. (K)					
		293.15		303.15		313.15	
		10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)
Mixed solvent systems : 0% DMF + water							
Glucose	0.0000	0.99820	-	0.99565	-	0.99222	-
	0.2048	1.01233	112.08	1.00972	112.81	1.00621	113.62
	0.4192	1.02627	112.60	1.02356	113.28	1.02000	114.00
	0.6439	1.03992	113.13	1.03722	113.68	1.03359	114.40
	0.8799	1.05335	113.63	1.05057	114.20	1.04688	114.92
	1.1282	1.06652	114.16	1.06368	114.73	1.06005	115.35
	1.3902	1.07937	114.74	1.07659	115.23	1.07288	115.86
	1.6675	1.09178	115.42	1.08909	115.83	1.08544	116.41
	1.9615	1.10396	116.09	1.10138	116.42	1.09783	116.92
	2.2748	1.11557	116.86	1.11320	117.09	1.10972	117.54
	2.6092	1.12685	117.66	1.12492	117.71	1.12147	118.14
	Mixed solvent systems : 10% DMF + water						
	0.0000	1.00863	-	1.00454	-	1.00042	-
	0.2028	1.02198	112.41	1.01781	113.30	1.01360	114.21
	0.4154	1.03508	113.05	1.03089	113.76	1.02663	114.59

Table-I (contd.)

0.6384	1.04796	113.63	1.04374	114.31	1.03938	115.17
0.8729	1.06059	114.22	1.05633	114.90	1.05195	115.70
1.1200	1.07299	114.81	1.06873	115.44	1.06426	116.27
1.3810	1.08510	115.44	1.08081	116.07	1.07627	116.90
1.6578	1.09071	116.24	1.09251	116.79	1.08803	117.53
1.9517	1.10807	117.00	1.10388	117.54	1.09955	118.15
2.2653	1.11890	117.88	1.11485	118.34	1.11042	119.00
2.6015	1.12912	118.89	1.12524	119.27	1.12106	119.79
Mixed solvent systems : 20% DMF + water						
0.0000	1.01123	-	1.00910	-	1.00377	-
0.2024	1.02438	113.12	1.02213	113.97	1.01675	114.87
0.4144	1.02730	113.71	1.03495	114.50	1.02949	115.44
0.6371	1.04991	114.40	1.04747	115.17	1.04201	116.00
0.8714	1.06223	115.12	1.05975	115.79	1.05421	116.67
1.1184	1.07433	115.76	1.07169	116.51	1.06626	117.23
1.3797	1.08597	116.57	1.08323	117.32	1.07789	117.95
1.6566	1.09733	117.34	1.09458	118.03	1.08947	118.50
1.9517	1.10805	118.32	1.10540	118.89	1.10059	119.20
2.2672	1.11820	119.39	1.11579	119.80	1.11125	120.00
2.6058	1.12784	120.50	1.12590	120.88	1.12164	120.77
Mixed solvent systems : 30% DMF + water						
0.0000	1.01427	-	1.01162	-	1.00823	-
0.2018	1.02709	114.42	1.02434	115.20	1.02082	116.26
0.4134	1.03970	114.95	1.03680	115.87	1.03315	116.88
0.6357	1.05200	115.62	1.04895	116.59	1.04521	117.56
0.8697	1.06404	116.29	1.06080	117.32	1.05702	118.20
1.1168	1.07560	117.16	1.07236	118.05	1.06858	118.83
1.3782	1.08686	117.98	1.08362	118.78	1.07922	119.61
1.6561	1.09760	118.94	1.09432	119.70	1.09052	120.39
1.9520	1.10795	119.90	1.10464	120.62	1.09967	121.41
2.2681	1.11790	120.86	1.11416	121.78	1.11021	122.20
2.6097	1.12670	122.20	1.12369	122.70	1.12008	123.22

cate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. Further, there occurs an increase in the values of V_{ϕ}^0 with increasing percentage of DMF in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems. This shows that the strength of solute-solvent interactions increases with increasing amount of DMF in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems. On perusing the values of S_v , it is seen that these are very small in comparison with those of V_{ϕ}^0 thereby showing the presence of weak solute-solute interactions in solutions of mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous medium as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems.

Partial molar volumes of transfer, $V_{2,tr}^0$, for mono-

and disaccharides from water to (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures have been computed from the following equation,

$$V_{2,tr}^0 = [V_2^0 \{(\text{DMF} + \text{water})\} - V_2^0 (\text{water})] \quad (3)$$

A perusal of results presented in Table 3 shows that in each case the values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ are positive and are rendered more positive with the increasing content of DMF in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems. The positive values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ may be explained in the light of different models^{23,24} mentioned below :

Partial molar volume (V_2^0) of a non-electrolyte at infinite dilution is a combination of the intrinsic volume (V_{int}) of the non-electrolyte and volume due to its inter-

Table 2. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_{ϕ}) for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Saccharides	$10^6 V_{\phi}^0$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)				$10^6 S_{\phi}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{kg mol}^{-2}$)			
	Water	10% DMF	20% DMF	30% DMF	Water	10% DMF	20% DMF	30% DMF
				Temp. : 293.15 K				
Glucose	111.60 (± 0.02)	111.88 (± 0.13)	112.43 (± 0.13)	113.59 (± 0.13)	2.30 (± 0.04)	2.68 (± 0.34)	3.05 (± 0.40)	3.24 (± 0.42)
Fructose	111.44 (± 0.13)	111.83 (± 0.02)	112.57 (± 0.13)	113.68 (± 0.13)	2.23 (± 0.29)	2.58 (± 0.04)	2.76 (± 0.36)	3.04 (± 0.39)
Sucrose	211.52 (± 0.16)	211.81 (± 0.16)	212.82 (± 0.15)	213.84 (± 0.16)	2.49 (± 0.39)	2.68 (± 0.42)	2.99 (± 0.45)	3.31 (± 0.52)
Maltose	228.45 (± 0.16)	229.84 (± 0.16)	230.96 (± 0.18)	231.79 (± 0.16)	2.29 (± 0.37)	2.55 (± 0.40)	2.81 (± 0.46)	3.09 (± 0.50)
				Temp. : 303.15 K				
Glucose	112.40 (± 0.01)	112.72 (± 0.13)	113.37 (± 0.13)	114.57 (± 0.13)	2.05 (± 0.02)	2.48 (± 0.32)	2.82 (± 0.37)	3.12 (± 0.41)
Fructose	112.25 (± 0.13)	112.81 (± 0.01)	113.50 (± 0.13)	114.70 (± 0.13)	2.06 (± 0.25)	2.41 (± 0.03)	2.48 (± 0.32)	2.81 (± 0.37)
Sucrose	212.32 (± 0.17)	212.84 (± 0.16)	213.84 (± 0.16)	214.76 (± 0.16)	2.25 (± 0.36)	2.44 (± 0.38)	2.74 (± 0.42)	3.11 (± 0.49)
Maltose	229.30 (± 0.16)	230.80 (± 0.16)	231.83 (± 0.17)	232.70 (± 0.17)	2.09 (± 0.34)	2.29 (± 0.36)	2.56 (± 0.48)	2.91 (± 0.48)
				Temp. : 313.15 K				
Glucose	113.22 (± 0.01)	113.67 (± 0.13)	114.46 (± 0.13)	115.68 (± 0.13)	1.89 (± 0.02)	2.34 (± 0.31)	2.44 (± 0.33)	2.89 (± 0.38)
Fructose	113.04 (± 0.14)	113.85 (± 0.02)	114.81 (± 0.14)	115.88 (± 0.13)	1.66 (± 0.23)	2.18 (± 0.04)	2.30 (± 0.30)	2.38 (± 0.31)
Sucrose	213.56 (± 0.16)	213.73 (± 0.16)	214.71 (± 0.15)	215.84 (± 0.16)	1.98 (± 0.30)	2.21 (± 0.34)	2.51 (± 0.36)	2.85 (± 0.44)
Maltose	230.55 (± 0.16)	231.85 (± 0.16)	232.76 (± 0.13)	233.83 (± 0.17)	1.76 (± 0.29)	2.07 (± 0.32)	2.34 (± 0.38)	2.66 (± 0.43)

Standard errors are given in parentheses.

Fig. 1. Variation of V_ϕ with m for solutions of glucose in 10% (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures : ($\square$) 293.15; (Δ) 303.15; ($\circ$) 313.15 K.

action with solvent (V_ϕ) which was further modified later as²⁴,

$$V_2^0 = V_{v,w} + V_{void} - V_{shrinkage} \quad (4)$$

where $V_{v,w}$ is the Van der Waals volume, V_{void} is the associated void²⁵ or empty volume and $V_{shrinkage}$ is volume of shrinkage. It has been assumed that $V_{v,w}$ and V_{void} have the same magnitude in water and in (DMF +

Table 3. Partial molar volumes of transfer ($V_{2,tr}^0$) for solutions of mono- and disaccharides from water to (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Saccharides	$10^6 V_{2,tr}^0$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		
	10% DMF	20% DMF	30% DMF
	Temp : 293.15 K		
Glucose	0.28	0.83	1.99
Fructose	0.39	1.13	2.24
Sucrose	0.29	1.30	2.32
Maltose	1.39	2.51	3.34
	Temp. : 303.15 K		
Glucose	0.32	0.97	2.17
Fructose	0.56	1.25	2.45
Sucrose	0.52	1.52	2.44
Maltose	1.50	2.53	3.40
	Temp. : 313.15 K		
Glucose	0.45	1.24	2.46
Fructose	0.81	1.77	2.84
Sucrose	0.17	1.15	2.28
Maltose	1.30	2.21	3.28

water) mixed solvent systems. Therefore, the positive values of $V_{2,tr}^0$ from water to (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems can be attributed to the decrease in the volume of shrinkage because of stronger interactions between DMF and hydroxy groups of mono- and disaccharides. Furthermore, these interactions will reduce the structure-breaking effect of DMF in water. In other words, more water is released as bulk water in the presence of mono- and disaccharides. Since bulk water has higher volume contributed than structure-broken water, therefore this factor will also contribute to positive value of $V_{2,tr}^0$ observed in the present study.

The densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of the solutions of mono- and disaccharides have been determined at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K) as a function of concentration (molality, m) in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of different compositions i.e. 0, 10, 20 and 30%, (w/w). The representative data in respect of solutions of glucose are presented in Table 4.

The viscosity-concentration data have been analysed in the light of the Jones-Dole equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{rel} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (5)$$

Table 4. Densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of solutions of mono- and disaccharides as a function of molality (m) in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures

Saccharides	Molality (m) (mol kg ⁻¹)	Temp. (K)								
		293.15		303.15		313.15				
		$10^{-3} \cdot \rho$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\frac{(\eta_{rel} - 1)}{\sqrt{m}}$	$10^{-3} \cdot \rho$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\frac{(\eta_{rel} - 1)}{\sqrt{m}}$	$10^{-3} \cdot \rho$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\frac{(\eta_{rel} - 1)}{\sqrt{m}}$
Glucose	0.0000	0.99820	0.9514	-	0.99565	0.7686	-	0.99222	0.6184	-
	0.2048	1.01236	1.0347	0.0720	1.00972	0.7916	-0.0170	1.00621	0.6376	-0.0520
	0.4192	1.02627	1.1499	0.2280	1.02356	0.8820	0.1630	1.02000	0.7285	0.1730
	0.6439	1.03992	1.2850	0.3520	1.03722	1.0022	0.3190	1.03359	0.8305	0.3240
	0.8799	1.05335	1.4569	0.4840	1.05057	1.1297	0.4430	1.04688	0.9425	0.4450
	1.1282	1.06652	1.6321	0.5920	1.06368	1.2738	0.5610	1.06005	1.0692	0.5550
	1.3902	1.07937	1.8207	0.6930	1.07659	1.4261	0.6670	1.07288	1.2069	0.6520
	1.6675	1.09178	2.0177	0.7850	1.08909	1.5880	0.7660	1.08544	1.3996	0.7840
	1.9615	1.10396	2.2580	0.8950	1.10138	1.7869	0.8840	1.09783	1.5767	0.8710
	2.2748	1.11557	2.5102	0.9980	1.11320	1.9725	0.9750	1.10972	1.8237	0.9940
2.6092	1.12685	2.7727	1.0940	1.12492	2.1846	1.0750	1.12147	2.0821	1.0930	
				Mixed solvent systems : 10% DMF + water						
0.0000	1.00863	0.8731	-	1.00454	0.6858	-	1.00042	0.5343	-	
0.2028	1.02198	0.9405	-0.1362	1.01781	0.7032	-0.2630	1.01360	0.5485	-0.3560	
0.4154	1.03508	1.0017	-0.0004	1.03089	0.7627	-0.0680	1.02663	0.6048	-0.1150	
0.6384	1.04796	1.1314	0.1616	1.04374	0.8614	0.1000	1.03938	0.6636	0.0200	
0.8729	1.06059	1.2618	0.2775	1.05633	0.9684	0.2290	1.05195	0.7655	0.1840	
1.1200	1.07299	1.4284	0.4021	1.06873	1.0898	0.3460	1.06426	0.8657	0.3074	
1.3810	1.08516	1.6777	0.4889	1.08081	1.2430	0.4750	1.07827	0.9840	0.4310	
1.6578	1.09671	1.7815	0.6042	1.09251	1.3941	0.5807	1.08803	1.1301	0.5670	
1.9517	1.10807	1.9811	0.6995	1.10388	1.5637	0.6874	1.09955	1.2920	0.7000	
2.2653	1.11890	2.2318	0.8155	1.11485	1.7656	0.8062	1.11042	1.4505	0.8110	
2.6015	1.12912	2.4938	0.9231	1.12524	1.9685	0.9100	1.12106	1.6014	0.9000	

Table-4 (contd.)

Mixed solvent systems : 20% DMF + water									
0.0000	1.01123	0.8486	-	1.00910	0.6646	-	1.00377	0.5087	-
0.2024	1.02438	0.9163	-0.1901	1.02213	0.6861	-0.3110	1.01675	0.5357	-0.4000
0.4144	1.03730	0.9870	-0.0232	1.03495	0.7325	-0.1270	1.02949	0.5775	-0.1800
0.6371	1.04991	1.0890	0.1088	1.04747	0.8391	0.0650	1.04201	0.6428	-0.0200
0.8714	1.06223	1.2141	0.2268	1.05975	0.9414	0.1930	1.05421	0.7508	0.1600
1.1184	1.07433	1.3673	0.3448	1.07169	1.0744	0.3280	1.06626	0.8556	0.2930
1.3797	1.08597	1.5430	0.4596	1.08323	1.2286	0.1599	1.07789	0.9854	0.4330
1.6566	1.09733	1.7520	0.5815	1.09458	1.3828	0.5699	1.08947	1.1240	0.5600
1.9517	1.10805	1.9715	0.6926	1.10540	1.5676	0.6909	1.10059	1.2818	0.6889
2.2672	1.11820	2.2241	0.8100	1.11579	1.7547	0.7967	1.11125	1.4339	0.7937
2.6058	1.12784	2.5151	0.9355	1.12590	1.9419	0.8886	1.12164	1.5811	0.8800
Mixed solvent systems : 30% DMF + water									
0.0000	1.0143	0.8249	-	1.0116	0.6414	-	1.0082	0.4945	-
0.2018	1.0271	0.9038	-0.2181	1.0243	0.6802	-0.3280	1.0208	0.5311	-0.4160
0.4134	1.0397	0.9556	-0.0721	1.0368	0.7269	-0.1380	1.0332	0.5658	-0.2080
0.6357	1.0520	1.0666	0.0809	1.0489	0.8091	0.0180	1.0452	0.6324	-0.0400
0.8697	1.0640	1.1944	0.2059	1.0608	0.9160	0.1590	1.0570	0.6910	0.0620
1.1168	1.0756	1.3523	0.3308	1.0724	1.0623	0.3139	1.0686	0.8002	0.2130
1.3782	1.0869	1.5225	0.4424	1.0836	1.2175	0.4483	1.0792	0.9270	0.3570
1.6561	1.0976	1.7602	0.5880	1.0943	1.3815	0.5687	1.0905	1.0642	0.4890
1.9520	1.1079	1.9800	0.6986	1.1046	1.5489	0.6740	1.0997	1.2373	0.6400
2.2681	1.1179	2.2140	0.8031	1.1142	1.7511	0.7936	1.1102	1.4185	0.7780
2.6097	1.1267	2.4444	0.8911	1.1237	1.9715	0.9109	1.1201	1.6240	0.9200

On expressing concentration in terms of molality (m), eq. (5) takes up the following form²⁶,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{\text{rel}} = 1 + A\sqrt{m} + Bm \quad (6)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)}{\sqrt{m}} = A + B\sqrt{m} \quad (7)$$

In the above eq (7), the coefficients A and B are the measure of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions²⁷ respectively. From eq. (7) it follows that the plot of $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{m}$ versus $\sqrt{m}$ should be linear. This has actually been found for (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition. These linear plots have been presented in representative Fig. 2. The values of coefficients A and B have been determined by computerized least square fitting of $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{m}$ versus $\sqrt{m}$ data to eq. (7) and are listed in Table 5 along with the standard errors (given in parentheses). It is seen that the values of A for mono- and disaccharides in 0% (DMF + water) i.e. in purely aqueous solutions (water) are negative. The same is true in the case of (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition. Further a perusal of Table 5 shows that the values of A are rendered increasingly more negative with increasing percentage of DMF in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures. This indicates that in purely aqueous solutions the solute-solute interactions are weak and these are further weakened with the increasing percentage of DMF in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems. On the other hand, the values of B coefficient are larger and positive in water as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of (DMF + water). This shows the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions in solutions of mono- and disaccharides in purely aqueous medium as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition. The larger positive values of B also indicate²⁷⁻²⁹ that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure-maker in water as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition.

The variation of V_{ϕ}^0 with the temperature can be expressed^{30,31} as below,

$$V_{\phi}^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_1T^2 \quad (8)$$

The values of coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 have been calcu-

Fig. 2. Variation of $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{m}$ with m for solutions of glucose in 10% (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems at different temperatures : (□) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15, (○) 313.15 K

lated from eq. (8) and are listed in Table 6.

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) have been calculated³⁰ from the following relation,

$$\phi_E^0 = (\partial V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T)_P = a_1 + 2a_2T \quad (9)$$

The values of ϕ_E^0 for mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition are presented in Table 7. A perusal of Table 7 shows that ϕ_E^0 tends to increase with

Table 5. Values of coefficients *A* and *B* of Jones-Dole equation for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Saccharides	<i>A</i> (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})				<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	Water	10% DMF	20% DMF	30% DMF	Water	10% DMF	20% DMF	30% DMF
				Temp. : 293.15 K				
Glucose	-0.344 (±0.12)	-0.574 (±0.12)	-0.654 (±0.16)	-0.694 (±0.12)	0.884 (±0.05)	0.918 (±0.05)	0.965 (±0.07)	0.984 (±0.05)
Fructose	-0.415 (±0.11)	-0.599 (±0.13)	-0.674 (±0.11)	-0.713 (±0.11)	0.922 (±0.05)	0.953 (±0.06)	0.987 (±0.05)	1.010 (±0.05)
Sucrose	-0.447 (±0.22)	-0.611 (±0.17)	-0.696 (±0.21)	-0.736 (±0.17)	0.985 (±0.09)	1.078 (±0.08)	1.102 (±0.10)	1.124 (±0.08)
Maltose	-0.468 (±0.15)	-0.674 (±0.18)	-0.771 (±0.26)	-0.795 (±0.23)	1.021 (±0.06)	1.096 (±0.08)	1.113 (±0.12)	1.130 (±0.11)
				Temp. : 303.15 K				
Glucose	-0.441 (±0.14)	-0.714 (±0.14)	-0.783 (±0.18)	-0.826 (±0.13)	0.940 (±0.06)	1.007 (±0.07)	1.048 (±0.09)	1.076 (±0.07)
Fructose	-0.490 (±0.18)	-0.731 (±0.12)	-0.810 (±0.14)	-0.842 (±0.12)	0.979 (±0.08)	1.034 (±0.06)	1.075 (±0.07)	1.086 (±0.06)
Sucrose	-0.505 (±0.21)	-0.779 (±0.18)	-0.837 (±0.23)	-0.870 (±0.17)	1.015 (±0.09)	1.0978 (±0.08)	1.121 (±0.11)	1.133 (±0.08)
Maltose	-0.532 (±0.21)	-0.798 (±0.21)	-0.893 (±0.22)	-0.904 (±0.22)	1.042 (±0.09)	1.120 (±0.10)	1.141 (±0.10)	1.148 (±0.10)
				Temp. : 313.15 K				
Glucose	-0.441 (±0.15)	-0.837 (±0.14)	-0.900 (±0.18)	-0.959 (±0.09)	0.965 (±0.07)	1.088 (±0.07)	1.124 (±0.10)	1.141 (±0.05)
Fructose	-0.518 (±0.16)	-0.857 (±0.17)	-0.914 (±0.11)	-0.978 (±0.12)	0.996 (±0.07)	1.094 (±0.09)	1.130 (±0.05)	1.156 (±0.06)
Sucrose	-0.542 (±0.20)	-0.886 (±0.15)	-0.957 (±0.21)	-0.982 (±0.20)	0.041 (±0.09)	1.124 (±0.07)	1.151 (±0.10)	1.164 (±0.10)
Maltose	-0.617 (±0.21)	-0.910 (±0.21)	-0.963 (±0.23)	-1.011 (±0.22)	1.068 (±0.09)	1.133 (±0.10)	1.162 (±0.11)	1.188 (±0.10)

Standard errors are given in parentheses.

Table 6. Values of coefficients *a*₁ for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition

Saccharides	Water				10% DMF				20% DMF				30% DMF			
	10 ⁵ .a ₀ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁸ .a ₁ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻¹)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ⁵ .a ₀ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁸ .a ₁ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻¹)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ⁵ .a ₀ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁸ .a ₁ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻¹)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ⁵ .a ₀ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁸ .a ₁ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻¹)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)	10 ¹⁰ .a ₂ (m ³ mol ⁻¹) K ⁻²)
Glucose	9.70	2.04	1.00	5.50	13.61	-24.40	5.50	15.15	-35.32	7.50	14.26	-28.96	6.50			
Fructose	30.10	-135.01	24.00	3.00	10.98	-3.09	3.00	25.42	-104.00	19.00	27.42	-116.32	21.00			
Sucrose	38.36	-123.19	22.00	33.00	48.67	-190.48	33.00	29.99	-66.34	12.50	25.80	-38.50	8.00			
Maltose	38.13	-110.76	20.00	4.50	24.17	-17.23	4.50	23.21	-9.19	3.00	30.29	-56.49	11.00			

Table 7. Limiting apparent molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) for various mono- and disaccharides in aqueous solutions of (DMF+water) at different temperatures

Saccharides	$10^6 \phi_E^0$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)											
	Water			10% DMF			20% DMF			30% DMF		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Glucose	0.079	0.081	0.083	0.079	0.090	0.101	0.087	0.102	0.117	0.092	0.105	0.118
Fructose	0.057	0.105	0.153	0.095	0.101	0.107	0.074	0.112	0.150	0.068	0.110	0.152
Sucrose	0.058	0.102	0.146	0.030	0.096	0.162	0.070	0.095	0.120	0.084	0.100	0.116
Maltose	0.065	0.105	0.145	0.092	0.101	0.110	0.084	0.090	0.098	0.087	0.102	0.121

rise in temperature. The increased values of ϕ_E^0 at elevated temperatures may be attributed³² to the structure making capacity of mono- and disaccharides.

Hepler³³ has proposed a method, by which qualitative information on solvation of solutes can be obtained from thermal expansion of aqueous solution by the following relation,

$$(\partial C_p^0/\partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$$

According to this, the left hand side of the above equation should be positive for all structure-breaking solutes and therefore, structure-breaking solutes possess negative value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$. On the other hand, positive value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ should be associated with structure-making solutes. In the present study the values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ have been obtained from eq. (8) and are listed in Table 8. It is seen that values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ for mono- and disaccharides are positive in purely aqueous medium (water) and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of

Table 8. Values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems

Saccharides	$10^{10} \cdot (\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ (m ⁶ mol ⁻² K ⁻²)			
	Water	10% DMF	20% DMF	30% DMF
Glucose	2.00	11.00	15.00	13.00
Fructose	48.00	6.00	38.00	42.00
Sucrose	44.00	66.00	25.00	16.00
Maltose	40.00	9.00	6.00	22.00

varying composition. The positive values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2)_p$ suggest that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure-makers in purely aqueous medium (water) as well as in the above mentioned mixed solvent systems.

The free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ per mole of solvent and solute respectively have been calculated as below :

The B coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation is related to the free energy of activation by the following equation³⁴,

$$B = \frac{V_1^0 - V_2^0}{1000} + \frac{V_1^0}{1000} \left[\frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}}{RT} \right] \quad (11)$$

where V_1^0 and V_2^0 are the partial volumes of the solvent and solute respectively. $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of solvent and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the free energy of

activation per mole of solute. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ are calculated using the following equation³⁵,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln \left[\frac{\eta_0 V_1^0}{hN} \right] \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{V_1^0} [1000B - (V_1^0 - V_2^0)] \quad (13)$$

where h is the Planck constant, N the Avogadro number, R the gas constant and T the temperature.

The entropy of activation ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow has been obtained from the following relation³⁴,

$$\frac{d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})}{dT} = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (14)$$

The enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow has been calculated with the help of following relation³⁴,

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (15)$$

The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ at different temperatures have been presented in Table 9. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for mono- and disaccharides in water and also in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition, are larger as compared to those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and

Table 9. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ for water and (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems and those of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying compositions at different temperatures

Solvent	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Water	9.195	8.976	8.713
10% DMF + water	9.074	8.785	8.435
20% DMF + water	9.259	8.964	8.576
30% DMF + water	9.412	9.106	8.736
	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
		Glucose	
Water	145.807	153.118	160.577
10% DMF + water	139.283	154.874	169.861
20% DMF + water	131.925	145.528	158.506
30% DMF + water	123.275	126.631	140.253
		Fructose	
Water	145.807	153.118	160.577
10% DMF + water	143.876	158.482	170.773
20% DMF + water	134.402	148.777	159.288
30% DMF + water	126.018	137.780	149.268

Table-9 (contd.)

		Sucrose	
Water	145.807	153.118	160.577
10% DMF + water	172.810	180.182	188.424
20% DMF + water	159.482	166.316	174.102
30% DMF + water	148.698	153.804	161.475
		Maltose	
Water	145.807	153.118	160.577
10% DMF + water	177.414	185.525	192.209
20% DMF + water	162.876	170.914	177.680
30% DMF + water	151.299	157.458	166.156

that in each case $(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}) > 0$. From this it is inferred that mono- and disaccharides behave as structure-makers³⁴ in water as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition.

The values of entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow for mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems have been calculated at different temperatures and presented in Table 10.

It is seen that values of both $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are negative in water as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition. From the negative values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems it follows that the transition state is associated with bond-making and an increase in order³⁴.

This suggests that slip-plane is in the disordered region.

Conclusion :

From the above discussion it is concluded that analysis of $V_\phi - m$ data in the light of the equation, $V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m$, and that of $\eta - m$ data in the light of Jones-Dole equation leads to the identical conclusions in regard to solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions in the solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems. Further, all the saccharides behave as structure makers in water as well as in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems.

Table 10. Values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ for solutions of mono- and disaccharides in water and in (DMF + water) mixed solvent systems of varying composition at different temperatures

Mixed solvent systems	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Glucose						
Water	-222.79	-230.39	-237.99	-76.98	-77.27	-77.42
10% DMF + water	-448.19	-463.48	-478.77	-308.91	-308.60	-308.91
20% DMF + water	-389.61	-402.90	-416.19	-257.69	-257.37	-257.69
30% DMF + water	-248.86	-257.35	-265.84	-125.58	-130.72	-125.58
Fructose						
Water	-222.79	-230.39	-237.99	-76.98	-77.27	-77.42
10% DMF + water	-394.24	-407.68	-421.13	-250.63	-249.20	-250.36
20% DMF + water	-364.76	-377.21	-389.65	-230.36	-228.43	-230.36
30% DMF + water	-340.79	-352.41	-364.04	-340.79	-214.63	-214.77
Sucrose						
Water	-222.79	-230.39	-237.99	-76.98	-77.27	-77.42
10% DMF + water	-228.86	-236.67	-244.47	-56.05	-56.48	-56.05
20% DMF + water	-214.30	-221.61	-228.92	-54.82	-55.30	-54.82
30% DMF + water	-187.28	-193.67	-200.06	-39.87	-38.59	-38.59
Maltose						
Water	-222.79	-230.39	-237.99	-76.98	-77.27	-77.42
10% DMF + water	-216.86	-224.26	-231.66	-39.45	-38.73	-39.45
20% DMF + water	-216.99	-224.39	-231.79	-54.11	-53.48	-54.11
30% DMF + water	-217.77	-225.20	-232.63	-66.47	-67.74	-66.47

Experimental

Glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose were of analytical reagents grade of 99.9 mol% purity and were used as such. The reagents were always placed in a desiccator over P₂O₅.

Freshly prepared doubly distilled water (sp. cond. ~ 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was used for preparing the binary mixed solvent systems of dimethyl formamide (DMF + water) of different compositions viz. 10, 20 and 30%, (w/w). Solutions were prepared in these solvent systems on molality scale. An electronic balance (Mettler) having an accuracy of 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ g was used for mass measurements.

Densities of the mixed solvent systems and solutions were measured at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 ± 0.01 K) using a digital vibrating tube densimeter (Anton Parr, Austria). The uncertainty in the density measurement was estimated to be ± 1 × 10⁻³ kg m⁻³. Viscosities of the solutions were measured at the desired temperature using an Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer as per details described by Findlay³⁶. Density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a thermostated bath, the temperature of which was maintained within ± 0.01 K of the desired values. The uncertainty of the viscosities was ± 1 × 10⁻⁴ mPa.s.

References

- G. G. Birch and S. Shamil, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1988, **84**, 2635.
- S. A. Galema and H. Hoiland, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 5321.
- G. G. Birch, J. Grigor and W. Derbyshire, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1989, **18**, 795.
- S. A. Galema, E. Howard, J. B. F. N. Engberts and J. R. Grigera, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1994, **265**, 215.
- R. K. Schmidt, M. Karplus and J. W. Brady, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 541.
- M. J. Tait, A. Suggett, F. Frank, S. Abbett and P. A. Quickenden, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1972, **1**, 131.
- A. Suggett, S. Abbett and P. J. Lillford, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 17.
- M. D. Danford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 3965.
- H. Uedaira, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1980, **53**, 2451.
- S. Shifrin and C. L. Parrott, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1975, **166**, 426.
- P. K. Banipal, T. S. Banipal, B. S. Lark and J. C. Ahluwalia, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1997, **93**, 81.
- P. K. Banipal, T. S. Banipal, B. S. Lark and J. C. Ahluwalia, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2000, **32**, 1409.
- P. K. Banipal, T. S. Banipal, B. S. Lark and J. C. Ahluwalia, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2002, **34**, 1825.
- T. S. Banipal, D. Kaur, G. Singh, B. S. Lark and P. K. Banipal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 1131.
- P. K. Banipal, G. Kaur and T. S. Banipal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 35.
- V. K. Syal, R. Gautam, B. S. Patial and S. Chauhan, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1999, **48**, 361.
- G. Jones and M. Dole, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
- G. R. Hedwig, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1988, **17**, 383.
- J. E. Desnoyers, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1982, **54**, 1469.
- G. R. Hedwig, J. F. Reading and T. H. Lilley, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, **87**, 1751.
- K. Belibagli and E. Agranci, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1990, **19**, 867.
- R. K. Wadi and P. Ramasami, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1997, **93**, 243.
- F. Franks, M. A. J. Quickenden, D. S. Reid and B. Waston, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **66**, 582.
- F. Shahidi, P. G. Farrell and J. T. Edward, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1977, **73**, 705.
- A. Bondi, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **58**, 929.
- A. S. Aswar, S. G. Kulkarni and P. G. Rohankar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1214.
- H. L. Zhang, G. H. Chen and S. J. Hen, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1997, **42**, 526.
- T. C. Bai, C. C. Huang, W. W. Yao and C. W. Zhu, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 2005, **232**, 171.
- J. J. Wang, Z. Yan and J. J. Lu, *J. Biophys. Chem.*, 2000, **86**, 71.
- P. S. Nikam, A. S. Sawant, J. S. Aher and R. S. Khainer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 197.
- B. S. Lark, P. Patyar, T. S. Banipal and N. Kishore, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2004, **49**, 553.
- A. Pal and S. Kumar, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2005, **117**, 267.
- L. Hepler, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 4613.
- D. Feakins, D. J. Freemantle and K. G. Lawrence, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1974, **70**, 795.
- S. Glasstone, K. Laidler and H. Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw Hill, New York, 1941.
- A. Findlay and J. A. Kitchner, "Practical Physical Chemistry", 8th ed., Longman, London, 1954.

